

Phenobarbiturato Complexes of Cu(II) in Methanolic Media

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Potentiometric determination of the stability constants of Cu(II)-phenobarbituric acid (HL) in methanolic media was made. The values found are :

$$\log \beta_{\text{CuL}_2}^{\text{Cu}^{2+}} = 9.45, \log \beta_{\text{CuL}_2\text{OH}^-}^{\text{CuL}_2} = 16.32, \log \beta_{\text{CuL}_2}^{\text{CuL}_2} = 16.32.$$

The potentiometric estimations were confirmed by spectrophotometric study.

PHENOBARBITAL or luminal (HL) (5-ethyl-5-phenyl barbituric acid), is a drug with hypnotic and anticonvulsive properties and has been used frequently as a treatment for epilepsy¹. It is soluble in organic solvents such as methanol, DMF, etc., but sparingly soluble in water. The activity mechanism of luminal is well-known².

Luminal acts as a monoprotic acid due to the tautomeric equilibrium in which a hydrogen is lost from the C²-OH group³. The pK_a value is 7.45 at 25° in phosphate buffer⁴.

The interaction between HL and metallic ions was first demonstrated by Zwickler⁵ who obtained a compound between Cu²⁺, HL and pyridine. This study was later used for the identification of HL and other derivatives of barbituric acid. The formation of ternary complexes has been studied by many authors⁶⁻¹¹ who have obtained compounds such as M(Barb)₂L₂ and M(Barb)L₂, where L is a base such as pyridine, imidazole, etc. Bult and Klasen¹² obtained compounds with the formulae M(Barb)₂, M(Barb)K, etc., and Delannoy *et al*¹³ obtained a compound of Cu²⁺ and barbituric acid with the formula M(Barb)₂.xH₂O.

In this work we report the interaction of Cu²⁺ ion and HL in methanol solution, using potentiometric methods.

Experimental

The following reagents were used : Recrystallized HL supplied by Bayer and Co., Cu(NO₃)₂.3H₂O, methanol (UCB, A.R.), NaOH (UCESOL) ampoules conserved and titrated¹⁴, tetrabutylammonium hydroxide (0.1 M) and NaClO₄ (Merck, R.A.).

pH measurements were carried out in a pHM 62 Radiometer with combined electrode GK 2401 C or glass electrode WJ-1 and calomel electrode K 4040, bathed in methanolic solution saturated with LiCl. Conductivity measurements were carried out in a Crison 522 conductimeter with a 1 cm conductivity cell Radiometer 26; the measurements were corrected¹⁴. Absorbance values were recorded in a

Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer model Hitachi 200 with Coleman S 1 cm quartz cell. The temperature was regulated at 25° with a Haake thermostat model F J.

In order to study complex formation between Cu(II) and HL, potentiometric and conductimetric titrations were carried out with aqueous NaOH solution, using combined electrode.

In the calculations of pK_a for HL as well as of stability constants in methanolic solutions, the pH was followed according to the technique of Ligny *et al*¹⁵⁻¹⁹ and Juillard *et al*²⁰. Tetrabutylammonium hydroxide was used as base so as to avoid precipitation. Temperature was maintained at 25 ± 0.2°.

Results and Discussion

Previous experiments have shown that formation of the different species depend upon three factors, viz. the concentration of Cu(II), pH and the HL/Cu molar ratio. To study the different complexes formed between Cu(II) and HL, a series of potentiometric and conductimetric titrations were carried out.

For 2.40 × 10⁻³ M Cu(II) solution potentiometric (Fig. 1) and conductimetric titrations suggest the following equilibria :

The CuL₂ species is green while the CuL₂²⁻ is violet, the latter develops a precipitate.

When Cu(II) concentration is one-tenth of the ligand (Fig. 2), the suggested equilibria are :

There is no violet colour in these solutions but there is blue colouration owing to CuL₂OH⁻ and CuL₂(OH)²⁻ ions. At this concentration a CuL₂²⁻

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration of methanolic solution of Cu—LH. $[Cu^{2+}] = 2.40 \times 10^{-3} M$ and different molar ratios LH/Cu; base = KOH (aq).

species forms when the ratio HL/Cu is greater than 14.

In both the cases, HL/Cu ratios below 2 give precipitates of Cu(II) basic salts.

In the determination of stability constants the following equations were used :

$$K_1 = \frac{m(H^+)^2}{C^2 \cdot (n-m)^2 \cdot (2-m)}$$

$$\beta_{CuL_2}^{Cu^{2+}} = K_1 \cdot K^2$$

$$K = \frac{(HL)}{(L^-)(H^+)} = \frac{1}{K_a}$$

$$K_2 = \frac{[C(m-2)OH^- - C(n-2)/1 + H^+K] \cdot (H^+)}{[C(3-m) + OH^- + C(n-2)/1 + H^+K] \cdot K_a}$$

$$\beta_{CuL_2OH^-}^{CuL_2} = K_2 \cdot \beta_{CuL_2}^{Cu^{2+}}$$

$$K_3 = \frac{[C(m-3)OH^- - C(n-2m+4) + 2OH^-/H^+K - 1] \cdot (H^+)}{\left[\frac{C(4-m) + OH^- + C(n-2m+4) + 2OH^-}{H^+K - 1} \right] \left[\frac{C(n-2m+4) + 2OH^-}{H^+K - 1} \right]^2}$$

$$\beta_{CuL_2^{2-}}^{CuL_2} = \beta_{CuL_2OH^-}^{CuL_2} \cdot K_3 \cdot K^2 \cdot K_a$$

where $n = HL/Cu$

$C =$ initial concentration of Cu(II)

$K_a =$ ionic product

K and K_a were determined from appropriate potentiometric titrations. The constants were also determined by methods described by Bjerrum and Rossotti-Rossotti²¹.

Table 1 contains the values for the formation constants of the species obtained at the two ionic strengths used, as calculated from the constants defined previously.

TABLE 1— pK_a OF HL, pK_b OF METHANOL AND STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR THE COMPLEXATION OF Cu(II) ION BY PHENOBARBITURIC ACID

	0.1 M NaClO ₄	1 M NaClO ₄
pK_a	15.30	14.80
pK_b	11.09	10.51
$\log \beta_{CuL_2}^{Cu^{2+}}$	10.80	9.45
$\log \beta_{CuL_2OH^-}^{CuL_2}$	18.01	16.32
$\log \beta_{CuL_2^{2-}}^{CuL_2}$	16.89	16.32

From Table 1 it can be concluded that CuL_2 complex is stable and prevents precipitation of basic salts of Cu(II) hydroxide. CuL_2OH^- and CuL_2^{2-} constants are very close to each other, which explains why it is difficult to obtain the second species at low HL/Cu ratio and low concentrations, since under those conditions $[OH^-]$ is maintained constant and relatively large. Thus, only when the HL/Cu ratio is greater than 14 there is enough L^- to form CuL_2^{2-} , which on the other hand is favoured by the insolubility of Na_2CuL_4 .

The effect of ionic strength is important in the formation of all the species and follows the order $CuL_2 < CuL_2OH^- < CuL_2^{2-}$, which is in agreement with the increased charge²².

The distribution diagram is given in Fig. 3. It can be concluded from the diagram that the species Cu^{2+} , CuL_2 , CuL_2OH^- and CuL_2^{2-} coexist in the pH region 7 to 9. Concentration of CuL_2 and CuL_2OH^- have a maximum at pH 7.5 and 8.5, respectively although they never become greater than 60%. The species CuL_2^{2-} predominates from pH 10 and is the only species at this pH range.

In order to verify these results a spectrophotometric study was carried out. The spectra of $4.65 \times 10^{-5} M$ solutions at different pH values and

HL/Cu = 14.2 are given in Fig. 4. The figure shows two isosbestic points at 740 and 565 nm, checked according to Nowicka methods²³. The presence of two isosbestic points, which confirms the existence of more than two species in solution, is in agreement with the potentiometric study and enables us to consider that at the isosbestic point 740 nm the species Cu^{2+} and CuL_2 coexist and at 565 nm CuL_2OH^- and CuL_2^{2-} coexist.

The absorption spectrum with $[Cu^{2+}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ and HL/Cu = 2.9 is given in Fig. 5. It shows an

Fig. 2. Potentiometric titration of methanolic solution of Cu-LH. $[Cu^{2+}] = 2.50 \times 10^{-3} M$ and different molar ratios LH/Cu; base = KOH (aq).

Fig. 3. Distribution diagram of species: 0 = Cu^{2+} , 1 = CuL_2 , 2 = CuL_2OH^- and 3 = CuL_2^{2-} .

Fig. 4. Absorption spectra of methanolic solution of Cu-LH: $[Cu^{2+}] = 4.65 \times 10^{-3} M$; LH/Cu = 14.1/1 at different pH, 1 = 6.19, 2 = 6.51, 3 = 6.91, 4 = 7.11, 5 = 7.18, 6 = 7.36, 7 = 7.61, 8 = 7.73, 9 = 8.01, 10 = 8.35, 11 = 9.01, 12 = 9.23, 13 = 9.47, 14 = 9.68 and 15 = 9.91; i = $NaClO_4$, 1 M; base = T₄NOH.

Fig. 5. Absorption spectra of methanolic solution Cu-LH: $[Cu^{2+}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; LH/Cu = 2.9/1 at different pH: 1 = 6.73, 2 = 7.19, 3 = 7.42, 4 = 7.57, 5 = 7.71, 6 = 8.09, 7 = 8.42, 8 = 8.98, 9 = 9.31 and 10 = 10.31 and 11 = 10.95; i = $NaClO_4$, 1 M; base = T₄NOH.

isosbestic point at 720 nm which indicates the simultaneous presence of CuL_2 and CuL_2OH^- species.

Verification of the number of species in each pH region was obtained using Coleman methods²⁴. For that purpose, a Basic program was written to the complexity of the equations.

Approximate calculation of the stability constants has been carried out using Vareille methods²⁵⁻²⁶. The values obtained are in agreement with those in Table 1.

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